

THE WAY TO IMPROVE THE NATIONAL ELECTION LEGISLATION IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract:

This article describes the main changes made in the national election legislation, the reasons for their origin, the way to step-by-step improvement of the new structure of the election code that fully meets international requirements, the advantages of the new election code and the main changes in it.

Key words: electoral code, changes in the electoral code, new electoral code, political parties, legal state, democratic, democratic election.

Topic relevance:In Uzbekistan, a democratic electoral system typical of democratic countries was formed during the historically short periods of independence. Elections are the main requirement of democracy. Because, in modern democratic states, elections are the main mechanism for the realization of people's sovereignty and form the "core" of democracy. Elections are an important political process that allows the people to exercise their political role as the source of state power. Elections are also considered a means of conveying the interests of different strata and groups to the institutions of state power. Elections are an important political event that shows the democratic image of the society, as well as the legal consciousness and thinking of the people. The reason is that there is no other process in society in which every citizen participates. Getting elected or being elected is not a simple matter. Feeling that the fate of our independent Motherland, its bright future lies at the root of these opportunities means that each of us is responsible for the future. Today's elections do not require indolence, but activism and political maturity.

Literature analysis from topic surface

One of the requirements of building a democratic society is holding democratic elections based on multi-party system. Every citizen will have the right to choose literally only when there is multi-party system.

It is known that in the past period of our country's independence, ample opportunities were created for the organization and further development of multi-party system. In particular, we can easily say that the first stage of the development of an independent state was a period of formation for political

parties, while the second stage was a period of comprehensive development for them. In both stages, political parties participated in the election process, gained their experience in the period from election to election, entered into close communication with the population, and managed to increase the number of supporters, including members. In this process, undoubtedly, the experience of political parties in using modern election technologies is also increasing.

Five political parties capable of representing and protecting the interests of broad social groups are operating in Uzbekistan today. These are:

- People's Democratic Party of Uzbekistan;
- "Adolat" social democratic party;
- Democratic Party of Uzbekistan "National Revival";
- Movement of entrepreneurs and businessmen - liberal-democratic party of Uzbekistan;
- Ecological Party of Uzbekistan.

Head of our state Shavkat Mirziyoyev spoke about the activities of political parties today: "Parties must satisfy the ideological and ideological needs of our citizens, especially our youth. If the parties fail to achieve this, there is no doubt that malicious forces will try to fill the gap." , - they made the task clear and understandable to the above-mentioned political parties based on the demands of the times.

The manner in which the election is held determines the current level of democracy in the country. Undoubtedly, elections, regardless of their form, are a very responsible process. Because this process expresses the will of the people. A citizen exercising his right to manage the state in this way can directly influence the formation of authorities only in this way. Islam Karimov, the First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, emphasized the role of free elections in the establishment of a democratic society and said, "As long as we are striving towards the noble goal of establishing a democratic legal state and a free civil society, it is the main demand of democracy. It is both a debt and a duty for us to properly organize such free elections. said.

1992 in order to establish a strong place of elections in the construction of a democratic legal state and the formation of the foundations of civil society in Uzbekistan.

On December 8, the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan was adopted. In the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, we can see the guarantees of citizens' electoral rights. Article 7 of our general dictionary states that "The people are the only source of state power, state power in the Republic of

Uzbekistan is exercised only by the authorities authorized by the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the laws adopted on the basis of the interests of the people." , important constitutional provisions have been strengthened, Article 32 states that "Citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan have the right to participate in the management of society and state affairs directly and through their representatives. Such participation is carried out through self-government, holding referendums and democratically organizing state bodies." the rule is defined. Article 60 states: "Political parties represent the political will of various classes and groups and participate in the establishment of state power through their democratically elected representatives." , is defined as The inclusion of Chapter XXIII, known as the "Electoral System", in the Constitution, on the one hand, ensures the constitutional strengthening of the main principles of the election, and on the other hand, these constitutional provisions serve as a foundation for the creation of electoral legislation.

The connection between elections and civil society is mainly determined by the fact that civil society is organized based on the diversity of opinions and interests of citizens. If the state bodies are not organized on the basis of fair elections with the participation of citizens, there will be no possibility to ensure voluntary obedience of citizens to the law and to avoid sharp social conflicts. Democratic elections deny that the issue of power can be resolved by force.

In the conditions of a civil society and a legal state, elections are not only a sign and manifestation of democracy, but also its necessary condition. Article 21 of the "Universal Declaration of Human Rights" adopted by the UN General Assembly on December 10, 1948 contains the following democratic principle: "Everyone has the right to participate in the governance of his country directly or through freely elected representatives. The will of the people should be the basis of the government's authority." .

Improvement of the democratic electoral legislation is the result of gradual reforms. In this regard, our modern country has followed a unique path. Including:

- in the conditions of democratization and renewal and liberalization of state administration, the change of the term of office of the President and the transfer of certain powers to the Senate of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Prime Minister, as well as the establishment of a bicameral parliament, led to changes in the law on elections came Therefore, on August 29, 2003, the new version of the Law "On Elections to the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan" was adopted and relevant amendments were made to the Law "On

Elections to Regional, District and City Councils of People's Deputies". and as a result, the necessary legal framework for elections to the bicameral parliament was created. It has international standards on the right to vote and experience in the development of the electoral system, as well as

-among the most important innovations introduced into the electoral legislation before the 2004 elections - the right of local councils to nominate candidates for deputies was canceled, a quota was set for women when political parties nominated candidates for deputies, and the issue of financing party activities during election campaigning was resolved. it should be emphasized;

- On April 30, 2004, the Law "On Financing of Political Parties" created an additional opportunity for the parties to conduct the pre-election campaign in an active and meaningful way;

- in addition, the law "On amendments and additions to certain laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan in connection with the improvement of electoral legislation" adopted on December 25, 2008 and effective from July 1, 2009 further developed the legal basis of the process. Also, taking into account the increasing role of political parties in the real processes taking place in the socio-political life of the society, the institution of nominating candidates for deputies from the initiative groups of voters was abolished. Also, the number of proxies of candidates for deputy has changed from 5 to 10. A number of new procedures have been introduced aimed at ensuring further strengthening of the transparency of election commissions during the preparation and conduct of the election;

At the joint meeting of the Legislative Chamber and the Senate of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan, on November 12, 2010, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan presented his program on the topic of "The concept of further deepening democratic reforms and development of civil society in our country" defined the main directions. One of these main directions is called "Ensuring freedom of suffrage and development of electoral legislation in Uzbekistan", in which the amendments and additions made to the electoral legislation in our country until today have been positively evaluated and the achievements achieved through their implementation are high. graded.

According to the words of the First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, IAKarimov: "During this period, many legal documents related to this field were adopted. All this led to the formation of an excellent legal framework that ensures the consistent and gradual liberalization of the national electoral system, the holding of bicameral parliamentary elections in full compliance with

the requirements of the law and generally recognized international principles and norms. .

The law of the Republic of Uzbekistan on September 4, 2014 "On Amendments and Additions to Certain Legislations of the Republic of Uzbekistan" has further strengthened the protection of the electoral rights of citizens by the court and the guarantee by the state. According to it, Chapter VI of the Code of Administrative Responsibility of the Republic of Uzbekistan, i.e. "Administrative responsibility for offenses in the field of organization and holding of elections and referendums" was established.

Result and discussion

As can be seen from the above, the electoral system in Uzbekistan is developing with changes in the Constitution and legal framework at each stage. Consistent application of electoral law in practice has been a component of democratic reforms implemented in the country. Compared to the past, not only the electoral system has developed, but also the voter's attitude to the election legislation, candidates, and political outlook have changed.

Indeed, a state that relies on the will of the people in terms of its organization and structure and activities, and strives to ensure the rights and freedoms of all people and citizens, is understood as a democratic state in the literal sense. In this, the democratic state is the guarantee, support and important integral component of the civil society based on the freedom and freedom of citizens. The basis of the unity of this country is the sovereignty of the people. On the other hand, the practical manifestation of the people's sovereignty is expressed by the state power established through free elections.

Creating the necessary legal norms and conditions to achieve the active participation of citizens in the ongoing works related to the comprehensive increase of social and political activity of the population, the renewal and reform of the country, the formation and improvement of legislation, representative power plays an extremely important role. In this regard, the gradual and systematic updating and improvement of the legal and legal norms of our legislation is crucial today. In this regard, the "Strategy of Actions" developed on five priority lines of development of the independent Republic of Uzbekistan and envisaging the development of the country in a short period of time is of particular importance.

In a word, our electoral system, which is considered an important component of the modernization of our country and democratic changes, is constantly improving. At the same time, today's life itself, especially the experience gained

during the last election, shows that the issues of further democratization of electoral processes in our country are being put on the agenda. In his address to the people of Uzbekistan in December, he said, "At this point, I would like to dwell on the electoral law, which is of great importance in our political life. 6 laws adopted in this regard and a number of by-laws, unfortunately, have not yet been consolidated into a single document. , and as a practical confirmation of this, in a very short period of time, i.e. on February 28 - March 1, 2019, at the plenary session of the chambers of the Oliy Majlis, the adoption of the "Electoral Code" shows how quickly the reforms in society have taken effect. it shows that it is giving.

Conclusion

In our opinion, based on the above, it can be concluded that the electoral legislation formed in Uzbekistan fully complies with the generally recognized international principles and norms related to the organization and conduct of elections, and it supports the establishment of a democratic legal state and civil society. is gradually improving in accordance with the goals of the implementation of the formation ideas.

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